

Effect of Raney Nickel on Some Dihydroxy Triterpenoids in High Boiling Solvents

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The effect of Raney nickel on three dihydroxy triterpenoids in boiling *p*-cymene has been studied. The two different types of reactions were observed which are: (a) dehydrogenation (oxidation) of the 3- and 28-OH groups, (b) saturation of easily reducible double bond, if present.

IN course of our investigation on reactions in high boiling solvents a study was made on the effect of Raney Ni on steroids¹⁻⁴ and monohydroxy triterpenoids⁵⁻⁷. The present communication deals with the course of reaction on three dihydroxy

Erythrodiol (Ia) when heated with Raney Ni in boiling *p*-cymene solution yielded olean-12-ene-3-one-28-al (Ib). The identity of (Ib) was accomplished from its analytical data, IR, NMR and mass spectra. For adequate confirmation this was converted to

Ia $R_1 = H, OH (\delta); R_2 = CH_2OH$

Ib $R_1 = O; R_2 = CHO$

Ic $R_1 = O, R_2 = COOH$

Id $R_1 = O, R_2 = COOCH_3$

IIa $R_1 = H, OH (\delta); R_2 = CH_2OH$

IIb $R_1 = O; R_2 = CHO$

IIc $R_1 = O, R_2 = COOH$

IIId $R_1 = O, R_2 = COOCH_3$

III

IVa $R_1 = O; R_2 = CHO$

IVb $R_1 = O; R_2 = COOH$

IVc $R_1 = O, R_2 = COOCH_3$

pentacyclic triterpenoids of oleanane, ursane and lupane series.

oleanonic acid (Ic) and methyl oleanonate⁸ (Id). The ketoaldehyde (Ib) has very recently being prepared

by Yosioka *et al*⁹ by the action of CrO₃-pyridine on erythrodiol, but the reported m.p. (142°-44°) is much lower than observed by us (168°-70°).

When uvaol (IIa) was refluxed with Raney Ni in a similar manner it furnished a new keto aldehyde, C₃₀H₄₆O₂, characterised as urs-12-ene-3-one-28-al (IIb) from its various spectrometric data and also by converting it to ursonic acid¹⁰ (IIc) and methyl ursonate (IIId).

Following the same procedure betulin (III) could be converted to the hitherto unreported dihydroketoaldehyde (IVa). In addition to various spectrometric data of (IVa) its conversion to (IVb)¹¹ and (IVc)⁷ unequivocally proved its identity.

Experimental

Preparation of Raney nickel catalyst: Raney Ni, W-2, was prepared by the action of NaOH aq. on Raney Ni aluminium alloy according to the method of Mozingo¹². The catalyst was used within a month of its preparation.

Purification of the solvent: *p*-cymene used in this reaction was prepared by refluxing the technical *p*-cymene with Raney Ni for 2-3 hr followed by distillation.

General Procedure: The triterpene was dissolved in *p*-cymene and to this was added Raney Ni which was previously washed with *p*-cymene. The mixture was heated on a sand bath and a few ml of *p*-cymene was distilled off, so as to ensure complete removal of alcohol and water by azeotropic process. The mixture was then heated under reflux on the sand bath for 10 hr. It was then filtered hot and the filtrate distilled in steam to remove *p*-cymene. The residue obtained was taken up in ether, ether removed, the residue dried and chromatographed over a column of neutral Brockmann alumina using solvents successively in the order of increasing polarity. The products obtained from different fractions were examined.

The petroleum used had b.p. 60°-80°. The weights of the catalyst were taken after the reactions were over. All m.p.s were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected. Rotations were determined in CHCl₃ solns at room temp. IR spectra were recorded as nujol mulls, NMR spectra were determined in CDCl₃ and TMS as internal standard, and the mass spectra were recorded at 70 eV.

Action of Raney nickel on erythrodiol: Erythrodiol was prepared by the reduction of methyl oleanolate with LAH in THF. To a solution of erythrodiol (470 mg) in *p*-cymene (25 ml), Raney Ni (2.5 g) was added and worked up as described above under 'general procedure'. The yellowish residue (390 mg) obtained was chromatographed on alumina (15 g.). The petroleum eluate yielded a white crystalline material, which on crystallization from MeOH afforded olean-12-ene-3-one-28-al (Ib) (250 mg), m.p. 168°-70°, [α]_D+82.2°, ν_{max} 1725, 2685 (aldehyde carbonyl), 1705 (six membered ring ketone), 838 cm⁻¹ (trisubstituted double bond); NMR: δ 9.35 (s, 1H,

-CHO), 5.4 (m, 1H, C-12H), 2.0 (m, 2H, protons *alpha* to the 3-keto group), 0.85-1.46 (seven methyls); mass: m/e 438 (M⁺, 23), 423 (M⁺ -CH₃, 5), 409 (M⁺ -CHO, 21), 232 (fragment *a*, 65), 203 (*a* -CHO, 100), 205 (fragment *b*, 38%) (Found: C, 82.18, H, 10.61; calc. for C₃₀H₄₆O₂: C, 82.14; H, 10.57%). The identity of the ketoaldehyde (Ib) was established by converting it to oleanonic acid (Ic), m.p. 299°-301° (Found: C, 79.15; H, 10.28; calc. for C₃₀H₄₆O₃: C, 79.25; H, 10.20%) and methyl oleanonate (Id), m.p. 184°, [α]_D+90°. (Found: C, 79.39; H, 10.40; calc for C₃₁H₄₈O₃: C, 79.44; H, 10.32%).

Action of Raney nickel on uvaol: Uvaol required for this experiment was prepared from ursolic acid in the usual way. Uvaol (700 mg) was dissolved in *p*-cymene (35 ml) and the solution was heated with Raney Ni (2.8 g). Working up in the usual way the residue (580 mg) obtained was chromatographed on alumina (20 g.). The material eluted with petroleum on crystallization from MeOH yielded colourless needles of urs-12-ene-3-one-28-al (IIb) (340 mg), m.p. 160°-61°, [α]_D+92.8°, ν_{max} 1725, 2690 (aldehyde carbonyl), 1705 (six membered ring ketone), 830 cm⁻¹ (trisubstituted double bond); NMR: δ 9.35 (s, 1H, -CHO), 5.42 (m, 1H, C-12H), 2.01 (m, 2H, protons *alpha* to the 3-keto group), 0.87-1.48 (seven methyls); mass: m/e 438 (M⁺, 21), 423 (M⁺ -CH₃, 6), 409 (M⁺ -CHO, 22), 232 (fragment *a*, 70), 203 (*a* -CHO, 100), 205 (fragment *b*, 40%). (Found: C, 82.02; H, 10.48; C₃₀H₄₆O₂ requires C, 82.14; H, 10.57%). The characterisation of (IIb) was confirmed by converting it to ursonic acid (IIc), m.p. 280°-84°, [α]_D+80°. (Found: C, 79.36; H, 9.98; calc. for C₃₀H₄₆O₃: C, 79.25; H, 10.20%) and methyl ursonate (IIId), m.p. 192°-93°, [α]_D+84°. (Found: C, 79.33; H, 10.17; calc. for C₃₁H₄₈O₃: C, 79.43; H, 10.32%).

Action of Raney nickel on betulin: Betulin was isolated from the roots of *Ecobolium linneanum*. Betulin (600 mg) in *p*-cymene (30 ml) and Raney Ni (2.5 g) were used. The ethereal extract (450 mg) after removal of the solvent and chromatographic separation followed by crystallization from MeOH afforded colourless needles of dihydrobetulonaldehyde (IVa) (230 mg), m.p. 196°-98°, [α]_D+3.3°, ν_{max} 2690, 1730 (aldehyde carbonyl), 1705 (six membered ring ketone); NMR: δ 9.7 (s, 1H, -CHO), 2.01 (m, 2H, protons *alpha* to the 3-keto group), 0.79-1.48 (seven methyls); mass: m/e 440 (M⁺, 100), 425 (M⁺ -CH₃, 16.5), 411 (M⁺ -CHO, 61) (Found: C, 81.68; H, 11.02; C₃₀H₄₈O₂ requires C, 81.76; H, 10.98%). The identity of the dihydroketoaldehyde (IVa) was confirmed by its conversion to dihydrobetulonic acid (IVb), m.p. 265°-68° (Found: C, 78.81; H, 10.63; calc. for C₃₀H₄₈O₃: C, 78.90; H, 10.59%) and methyl dihydrobetulonate (IVc), m.p. 188°-89°, [α]_D+7°. (Found: C, 79.19; H, 10.63; calc. for C₃₁H₅₀O₃: C, 79.10; H, 10.71%).

Discussion

Thus it appears that this procedure is useful in the preparation of 3-keto, 28-aldehydes from corresponding dihydroxy pentacyclic triterpenes as the yield

of the products is comparatively good and the ketoacids which are usually associated with the ketoaldehydes in other oxidation process have not been encountered in this method. The process involves dehydrogenation (oxidation) of 3- and 28-hydroxyl groups *cum* hydrogenation of easily reducible double bonds, if present. As regards the hydrogenation of the easily reducible double bond it was observed in the earlier cases of steroids⁴ and triterpenoids⁷ that hydrogen necessary for the purpose is supplied from the reacting molecules and not from the Raney Ni itself. Most probably this also holds good in the formation of dihydroketoaldehyde (IVa).

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